

CUSP HUMAN RISK ASSESSMENT OF MNPs- THE IMPTOX APPROACH

PRACTICE-BASED ANALYSIS OF DATA NEEDS, AVAILABILITY, REUSE AND GAPS FOR MNP-RISK RELATED TOOLS

21ST APRIL 2023

The Imptox project has received funding from the EU's H2020 framework programme for research and innovation under grant agreement n. 965173

IMPTOX OBJECTIVES: HUMAN EXPOSURE AND CLINICAL IMPACT OF MNPs

Exposure Analytical tools Exposure levels Cargo identification *In vitro* health impacts *In vivo* health impacts Human health impacts

MNPs exposure impact

Effects of MNPs exposure on allergy

- 8 WP- chemistry, microbiology, in vitro studies, animal studies, clinical study
- **Biomonitoring** (acute toxicological and other “indirect” adverse effects on human health)
- Identification and characterization of MNPs in different biological samples

IMPTOX DATA REQUIREMENTS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

- Biological samples (human, cell culture, animal)
- Food and water samples
- Clinical data (personal and family history, allergy status)
- Dietary and lifestyle habits
- Data on exposure to and awareness of use of MNPs

IMPTOX DATA SOURCES

- Field work in the clinical study recruitment
- Clinical facilities (detailed allergy testing, follow up)
- Animal facilities (mice and marine models)
- In vitro labs (cell culture, microbiology)

CLINICAL STUDY- CROATIA

- Recruitment of paediatric population cohort based on differential exposure and susceptibility
- School children (N= > 700, 6-18 yrs)
- Healthy controls and children with allergic diseases
- **Recruitment almost finished**
- 2 continental regions (Zagreb and surroundings) and Slavonia 1 Mediterranean region
- Follow up after 6 months

ACHIEVEMENTS

- Recruitment status (as of 22nd March 2023)

PARTICIPANT STRATIFICATION

ALLERGIC DISEASE BY STUDY SITE

SENSITIZATION (FOOD OR INHALED) BY STUDY SITE

MANY THANKS TO ALL WP8 MEMBERS!

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

- Happy to discuss and answer any questions!

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